

Baby steps in the use of RF Diffusion to modulate transcriptional regulators

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RF Diffusion – and friends – exist

- “I want a de novo designed protein that binds my target protein (which has a known structure)”

Could be useful for TFs

- “Undruggable” – small domains that are largely convex – lacking pockets
- Either as drugs or just as probes of function
- One TR we work on is a chromatin remodelling enzyme – CHD4
- Pushes nucleosomes around to expose or conceal promoters

DNA dreadlocks

Felsenfeld and Groudine (2003) *Nature* 421, 448
DuPraw (1968) *Cell and Molecular Biology*

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Chromatin remodelling enzymes + complexes

Histone eviction

Nucleosome sliding

Exchange of histone variants

Nucleosome unwrapping

Most remodellers share a translocase domain...

Hauk (2010) Mol Cell 39, 711; Liu (2017) Nature 544, 440
Farnung (2017) 550, 539; Li (2019) Nature 567, 409
Eustermann (2018) Nature 556, 386; Zhang (2023) Science 381, 313

...but vary in their auxiliary domains

- Found at promoters of ~all active genes in all tissues
- Essential for development
- Can activate or repress genes...but we don't really know how
- CHD4 is a major cancer susceptibility

A real-time bulk fluorescence assay for remodelling

The N-terminal region promotes remodelling

The N-terminal region acts like a ratchet pawl

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Can we develop HMG inhibitors using RFDiffusion?

We started small – 30 predictions

We chose the 'best' six

We chose the 'best' six based on AF corroboration

Binder 2

Binder 8

Binder 10

Binder 15

Binder 19

Binder 20

Level 1 – RFD makes well-ordered proteins

Binder 2

Binder 8

Binder 10

Binder 15

Binder 20

Binder 19

Level 2 –RFD proteins bind their target!

The other Binders also showed binding

The other Binders also showed binding

Affinities from NMR titration data

200 μM

Binder 2

100 μM

Binder 15

190 μM

Binder 8

X

Binder 19

1 μM

Binder 10

1300 μM

Binder 20

Binding surfaces from NMR titration data

Level 3 – designed binding mode confirmed

■ RFD prediction

■ ■ Structural model from
NMR data + HADDOCK

But do they do anything?

Yes

Yes

Activity is in line with affinity

Binder	KD (μM)
10	1
15	100
20	1300

Takeaways from round 1

- Expressed binders all had high-quality NMR spectra => well-ordered and well-behaved
- All binders (that expressed) bound to the target
- Best binder bound in exactly the predicted manner – and it impacted function

Develop candidate CHD4 inhibitors using RFdiffusion

Can we scale up?

Ivan Jansen

Lihua Yang

Can we scale up?

80-100
residues

101-120
residues

121-140
residues

141-150
residues

The gels

The SPR data

The SPR data

SPR success rate: 9/59

Binder	KD (μM)
A6	2
C4	3
C12	1
D1	1
E1	2
E2	6
F1	5
G3	0.02
G4	0.03

HMG-G3 and HMG-G4 structures

HMG-G3

$\text{RMSD}_{\text{AF}} = 0.6 \text{ \AA}$
145 residues

HMG-G4

$\text{RMSD}_{\text{AF}} = 0.6 \text{ \AA}$
145 residues

Lihua Yang

Jordan

Milad

But do they do anything?

But do they do anything?

Takeaways from round 2

- More is better (and Ivan has PTSD)

HMG-B10

110 residues
KD = 1000 nM

HMG-G4

145 residues
KD = 15 nM

But is there a better way?

But is there a better way?

But is there a better way?

Chose top **2000** sequences <85aa
Ordered from Twist as oligo pools

Picked the top 10 most enriched binders

EEKLKELIAEHEEKFLKLMEEKDLPDEEFWKLIIEFVAEFEKELEELKKS

SAREARLEAYRKEIDAMAKEAKEKNLTYEEILERVVAFLEKAEKDPRMTPEDLEALADYLIIEKFAPLFDKALAAEKA

But is there a better way?

50-65 aa

65-85 aa

Binder	KD (nM)
R20.1	-
R25.1	0.6
R25.2	15
R25.3	600
R25.4	15,000
R25.5	500

But is there a better way?

50-65 aa

65-85 aa

Binder	KD (nM)
R20.1	-
R25.1	0.6
R25.2	15
R25.3	600
R25.4	15,000
R25.5	500

After three rounds of design/selection...

HMG-B10

110 residues
KD = 1000 nM

HMG-G4

145 residues
KD = 15 nM

HMG-RR25

85 residues
KD = 0.6 nM

Takeaways from round 3

- Could be a useful way to take a shortcut
- mRNA display is tricky to set up – but other approaches like yeast surface display might be more straightforward
- Overall, RFD makes extremely well-behaved proteins – quite amazing
- A ton of applications

